

Synthesis and antimicrobial studies of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}-complexes with Schiff bases

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Complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with Schiff base ligands by condensation of thioacetamide or 4-aminoacetanilide with 2-furfuraldehyde or 4-chlorobenzaldehyde have been synthesized. Some of the complexes have been screened for their antimicrobial activities.

Studies of new types of chemotherapeutically important Schiff bases and metal co-ordinated drugs are now attracting much attention¹. The aim of this study is to observe the impact of chelation on the therapeutic value of the organic compounds. Some Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes have been synthesized involving the biopotent ligands, viz. furfurylidene-thioacetamide (FTA), furfurylidene-4-aminoacetanilide (FAA) and 4-chlorobenzylidene-thioacetamide (CTA).

2-Furfurylidene-thioacetamide (FTA)

4-Chlorobenzylidene-thioacetamide (CTA)

2-Furfurylidene-4-aminoacetanilide (FAA)

Results and discussion

Complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with FTA : The analytical data reflect the metal-to-ligand stoichiometry to be 1 : 1. The molar conductance values in methanol (10⁻³ M) suggest that the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are of uni-bivalent electrolytic nature while the Co^{II} is non-electrolyte.

The IR band due to azomethine group in the ligand (1650 cm⁻¹) has shifted to lower frequency side (1620 ± 10 cm⁻¹) in the metal complexes due to co-ordination through azomethine nitrogen². A medium intensity ligand band at 1210 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C) shifts down (1180 ± 10 cm⁻¹) in complexes due to chelation through ring oxygen^{2,3}. A band due to C=S stretching (1525 cm⁻¹) remains unchanged in the complexes ruling out its participation in complex formation. The bands due to stretching and rocking vibrations of water appear in the complex spectra at 3430 ± 10 and 760 ± 10 cm⁻¹ respectively, suggesting the presence of co-ordinated water molecules. The new bands in the spectra of complexes around 510 ± 10 and 410 ± 10 cm⁻¹ are assigned to M-O and M-N bonding, respectively^{3,4}.

The electronic spectrum of Co^{II}-FTA complex shows two bands at 15340 and 24430 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(F) (ν₂) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν₃) transitions, respectively. The values of 10 Dq, λ, B, β and LFSE are 8221 cm⁻¹, (-)618, 961 cm⁻¹, 0.85 and 78.43 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively, which are in fair agreement with the predicted values of octahedral complex. The absorption spectrum of Ni^{II}-FTA complex shows two bands at 18610 and 27320 cm⁻¹, assignable to ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{2g}(ν₂) and ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g}(ν₃) transitions, respectively. The diamagnetic nature of the complex and transitions suggest the geometry to be square planar. The two bands in the Cu^{II}-complex at 12480 and 19265 cm⁻¹ corresponds to transitions ²B_{1g} → ²B_{2g} and ²B_{1g} → ²E_g, favouring square-planar geometry⁴⁻⁶.

Complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with FAA : The analytical data of the complexes show that the metal to ligand stoichiometry is 1 : 1. The conductivity data of the complexes in methanol (10⁻³ M) suggest their uni-bivalent

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of the complexes

Compd.	Colour	M.p./dec°C	μ_{eff} B.M.	Conductivity $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
$\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{NOS}$ (FTA)	Brown	85°	—	—
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{NOS})\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Brown	115° (d)	5.06	36.6
$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{NOS})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Orange	110° (d)	Diamag.	170.0
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{NOS})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Brown	122° (d)	1.94	160.0
$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ (FAA)	Black	120°	—	—
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot \text{Cl}_2$	Brown	223° (d)	4.54	140.0
$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot \text{Cl}_2$	Brown	212° (d)	Diamag.	135.0
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot \text{Cl}_2$	Brown	217° (d)	1.91	150.0
$\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{NCIS}$ (CTA)	Yellow	90°	—	—
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{NCIS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	Brown	130° (d)	5.04	24.0
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{NCIS})_2\text{Cl}_2$	Green	140° (d)	3.06	35.2
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{NCIS})_2\text{Cl}_2$	Green	136° (d)	2.04	29.4

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and metal analyses.

electrolytic nature.

The IR ligand band at 1590 cm^{-1} shifted to lower side by $15\text{--}20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes suggesting participation of azomethine nitrogen in co-ordination. The ligand's furan C-O-C band (1125 cm^{-1}) shifts higher ($1155 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in complexes suggesting chelation through the ring oxygen^{2,4}. The bands around 3440 ± 10 and $760 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes are assignable to co-ordinated water molecules. The bands at 540 ± 10 and $470 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ respectively^{3,4}.

The electronic spectrum of Co^{II} -FAA complex shows one band at 16200 cm^{-1} for ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g(\text{P})}$ transition. The magnetic moment value for this complex is 4.54 B.M.; hence the tetrahedral geometry has been suggested. In Ni^{II} -complex three bands at 15240, 18210 and 21120 cm^{-1} have been assigned to ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{E}_g$, ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{2g}$ and ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{1g}$ transitions, respectively. This complex is diamagnetic, therefore a square planar geometry has been suggested. The electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} -complex shows bands at 14040 and 18450 cm^{-1} , assignable to transitions ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{2g}$ and ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$, favouring square planar geometry⁴⁻⁶.

Complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with CTA : The analytical data of the metal complexes indicate metal-to-ligand (Schiff base) stoichiometry for all the three complexes as 1 : 2. The molar conductance values in methanol (10^{-3} M) suggest that the complexes are non-ionic in nature. The observed magnetic moment values are 5.04, 3.06 and 2.04 B.M. for the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, respectively.

The IR ligand band at 1630 cm^{-1} shifted to lower side ($1600 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in complexes, due to co-ordination through azomethine nitrogen. The ligand band due to C=S at 1520 cm^{-1} shifts down ($1490 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the complexes indicating about its chelation. The new band at $470 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes is due to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ ²⁻⁴.

The electronic spectrum of Co^{II} -CTA complex shows two bands at 17800 and 19680 cm^{-1} corresponding to transitions ${}^4\text{T}_{1g(\text{F})} \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g(\text{F})}$ and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g(\text{F})} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g(\text{P})}$ respectively. The values of $10 Dq$, B , β , λ and LFSE are 9468 cm^{-1} , 833 cm^{-1} , 0.74, ($-$) 699 cm^{-1} and $90.33 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. This suggests the geometry of the Co^{II} -complex be octahedral. The Ni^{II} -complex exhibits three bands at 11140, 16940 and 25430 cm^{-1} corresponding to transitions ${}^3\text{A}_{2g(\text{F})} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g(\text{F})}$, ${}^3\text{A}_{2g(\text{F})} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g(\text{F})}$ and ${}^3\text{A}_{2g(\text{F})} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g(\text{P})}$, respectively. The values of $10 Dq$, B , β , λ and LFSE are 11140 cm^{-1} , 725 cm^{-1} , 0.67, ($-$) 213 and $150.26 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. This confirms the octahedral geometry. The Cu^{II} complex gives a single broad band at $12600\text{--}16310 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (${}^2\text{E}_g \rightarrow {}^2\text{T}_{2g}$ transition). The values of $10 Dq$, λ and LFSE are 13836 cm^{-1} , ($-$) 1239 cm^{-1} and $99.00 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, respectively favouring an octahedral geometry⁴⁻⁶.

ESR studies : The esr spectra of Cu^{II} -FTA and Cu^{II} -CTA complexes were recorded on X-band frequency at 9.07 GHz under the magnetic field strength of 2000 ± 2000 and 3000 ± 2000 gauss respectively at temperature 30° . They exhibit Lorentzian type of peaks. The values of parameters g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , g_{av} , G and Δg are 2.2367, 2.1805, 2.19992, 1.3113 and 0.0562 respectively for Cu^{II} -FTA complex; and 2.2329, 2.1768, 2.1955, 1.3167 and 0.0561

respectively for Cu^{II}-CTA complex^{7,8}.

The values of g_{\parallel} (>2) indicate the prevalence of covalent character in the M-L bond. This also suggests the interaction between the Cu-Cu centers in solid state. The value of axial symmetry parameter G for these complexes is appreciably less than 4, indicating the strong field nature of the ligand. The correlation $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2$ suggests a tetragonally elongated or square planar structure with the ground state $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ^{7,8}.

Antimicrobial activity : All the twelve compounds (Schiff bases and complexes) were evaluated for their antibacterial and antifungal activities against *M. tuberculosis*, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *S. typhi*, *A. niger*, *C. albicans* and *R. oryzae* at a concentration of 25 and 50 µg ml⁻¹ employing the disc method⁴⁻⁸. All the metal chelates exhibited activities (zone of inhibition 8–22 mm). In general, metal complexes are more active than the Schiff bases. The antimicrobial activity of the metal chelates was found to be in the order : Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} ≥ Co^{II}.

Experimental

The Schiff bases (ligands) were synthesized by refluxing an equimolar amounts of 4-chlorobenzaldehyde or 2-furfuraldehyde and 4-aminoacetanilide or thioacetamide in methanolic medium on a water bath for 3–6 h. The resulting products were crystallised with methanol.

The metal complexes were prepared by refluxing a mixture of methanolic solutions of metal salt MCl₂.nH₂O and ligand (FTA and FAA in 1 : 1 or CTA in 1 : 2 M-L ratio) on a water bath for 4–6 h. The coloured precipitate that appeared on cooling was dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl₂ in a dessicator and also in an electric oven at 70°. The purity of the compounds was checked

by TLC using silica gel.

M.p. was determined on a Toshniwal CL-0301 apparatus. Electronic spectra (MeOH) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 2B spectrophotometer. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded at C.D.R.I., Lucknow, and ESR spectra at I.I.T., Mumbai. Magnetic moment was measured at RT by the Gouy's technique. Conductance was measured on an Elico-CM82 conductivity bridge. The antimicrobial studies were done at the Botany Department of Sagar university and also by TAACF, Birmingham (U.K.).

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